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Title: Integrating forced migrants in a research and communication project using the principles of RRI

Abstract:

The application of Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) to migration studies and communication represents a clear interpretative and methodological advantage. RRI provides a more holistic vision for the understanding of the phenomenon and focuses on a co-design 'with and for' the migrants and 'with and in' the society. Furthermore, RRI emphasizes the inclusiveness, open participation, transparency, and responsive change with local responses to address global challenges. To that end the concept of 'quintuple helix', one of the principles of RRI, is essential. This is to include in the whole research, innovation and communication process the stakeholders who represent the different social actors, including civil society (NGOs and citizens, considering forced migrants themselves), academy and education (e.g., universities and research centers), policy makers (local and national, related with migration and refugee policy), and business world.

Following the quintuple helix, 7 action-research units (ARUs) have been created in Jordan, Lebanon, Turkey, Hungary, Finland, Italy, and Spain to co-design different tailored attention and inclusion strategies (TAIS) for distinctively vulnerable people among the forcibly displaced. Due to that, with the application of RRI, migrants and forced migrants can become the focus of the innovation and communication processes.

The participation in the project was limited to those people who felt psychologically benefited by their participation in the Project, following the protocols and considerations established by RAISD Ethics Plan previously approved by the European Commission. Forced migrants in these 7 ARUs actively participated in the design and evaluation of the TAISs. In addition, some forced migrants have been key providers of services for the implementation of certain tailored attention and inclusion strategies.

Significative communication results have also been achieved thanks to the participation of 17 people belonging to diverse profiles among forced migrants in a documentary film and other transmedia items. The active participation of forced migrants enriches the experience of all stakeholders. As stated by a representative of an NGO collaborating with RAISD: 'A very important asset has been that in these spaces of joint work there has been something that is evident, but infrequent, which is the participation of the displaced people. Their experience at origin, on transit, on arrival, in the procedures, in the responses, in the reception... It is essential to be able to improve, redesign and establish strategies'.

However, the inclusion of vulnerable groups among forced migrants in all research, innovation and communication processes also poses several challenges. Even more with online activities due to the pandemic. Difficulties such as language, digital divide, the characteristics of the host

society, migratory grief, educational level, or lack of self-assurance to collaborate on equal terms with the rest of stakeholders require prior training and careful preparation, so that their participation in the research project and its communication can be fully effective, significant, and diverse.

This compilation of advances, challenges and recommendations derived from the specific cases in these 7 countries are of great importance for the development and adaptation of future research and communication projects.

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